

ORGANIZING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN THE EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

Akhmedova Zulhumor Ikromovna

Asian International University

Teacher of "General technical sciences" department

akhmedovazulhumor85@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10570475>

INTRODUCTION

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5349 of February 19, 2018, "On measures to further improve the field of information and communication technologies", No. PQ-2909 of April 20, 2017 "Further development of the higher education system on measures" No. PQ-5099 dated June 30, 2017 "On measures to fundamentally improve the conditions for the development of information technology in the Republic", No. PQ-3775 dated June 5, 2018 No. PQ-4851 dated October 6, 2020 "On additional measures to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensure their active participation in comprehensive reforms implemented in the country" The decision "On measures to further improve the education system in the field of information technologies, develop scientific researches and integrate them with the IT industry" and other similar regulatory legal documents related to this activity. Article research serves a certain level.

ORGANIZING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN THE EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

Organization of educational process in Moodle educational information system. Educational process in the Moodle educational information system. To install the Moodle server, you need to use a hosting service. There are several ways to install the Moodle server.

When choosing a hosting service, you should conduct an analysis of the full compatibility of the server, the necessary space and resources.

When using the Moodle educational information system, the educational institution provides access to the educational-methodical complex through the network of students, professors and teachers. This educational-methodical complex includes the following:

- the State educational standard of the field of study or specialty;
- Model program created in accordance with the state education standard;
- the purpose and tasks of science, the content of lectures, seminars, practical and laboratory exercises, topics of control and course work, issues,

assignments, final control questions, and educational and methodological support of science, organization of independent work incorporating a working program instructions;

- educational-methodical map and calendar thematic plans;
- electronic versions of textbooks, study guides and other educational materials;
- methodological instructions on the use of pedagogical and information technologies in training;
- methodical provision of practical and laboratory trainings that form skills and competencies in the application of theoretical knowledge;
- training and qualification practice program, methodological guide on its organization;
- control assignments and tests aimed at determining the level of mastery of theoretical and practical educational materials;
- distribution of points for current, intermediate and final controls in the subject, type of tasks, evaluation criteria.
- Educational-methodological complex, reference books and dictionaries if necessary, periodicals, field publications and socio-political publications, scientific literature and chronographies, references to the database, sites, information systems and others can be filled with network resources.

The educational process in the Moodle educational information system is organized on the basis of the following documents:

- educational process graph;
- working curriculum for the field;
- training programs in subjects, control work (with deadlines for their completion);
- schedule of training sessions during the inter-session period;
- journal of recording control work;
- summary record of rating control results;
- journal of students' participation in the seminar forum;
- a journal of registration of the acceptance of control work and consultations held through the network.
- The PO' and the head of the department are responsible for the quality of the taught subject.
- The following general requirements for e-learning courses to be included in the system can be obtained:

- introduction to the subject (history, subject, relevance, interrelationship and place of the specialty program with other subjects);
- study program on science (course);
- goals and tasks of studying science;
- methodological instructions for independent study of the course;
- content;
- main table of contents organized by sections;
- theoretical and practical information on departments, tests, questions, exercises with answers for training;
- final test;
- practical assignments for independent work;
- topics for minor research (mini-ITI);
- Glossary (explanatory dictionary of terms);
- list of abbreviations and terms;
- summary;
- literature (main , additional, optional);
- chrestomatiya (digest) taken from textbooks, magazines and including slides of scientific articles on the topics of the course;
- brief information about the author of the manual.

Moodle is the main electronic educational content in the educational information system. Their purpose is to summarize and systematize materials studied independently by students, to highlight the most important, basic and complex issues of the course. Lectures are uploaded to the system in the form of video or multimedia lectures prepared on the basis of pedagogical software tools. Video or multimedia lectures are distributed through the Moodle educational information system.

PRACTICAL LESSONS give students the opportunity to solve the most common problems, the elements of which exist in all related disciplines, to acquire the skills of making calculations, to learn how to use references under the guidance of the teacher. Practical training helps to strengthen and deepen the theoretical knowledge acquired by the student. After each lecture session, educational elements related to practical training are placed.

SEMINARS is the main form of practical training in the humanities . The peculiarity of this type of training is that during the seminar conversation, students learn to justify their opinion, express it logically, quickly find answers to the questions, and learn to use primary sources correctly. It is recommended

to organize the workshop through the "learning elements" available in the Moodle educational information system.

LABORATORY TRAINING gives students an opportunity to get an idea of how to set up and conduct an experiment correctly, to acquire the skills of working with modern laboratory and measuring equipment, in which students can analyze the results of experiments, prepare a report on the work performed. they learn. During laboratory sessions, students compare the results of experiments with the existing rules of the theory, which allows for a deeper acquisition of theoretical knowledge.

Teaching scenario in the Moodle educational information system. In addition to educational tools that meet the requirements of modern technologies, the role of a skillfully structured lecture text and a teaching scenario representing the sequence of actions in the teaching process is very important for the effectiveness of teaching in the Moodle educational information system. .

A teaching scenario is a sequence of actions to be performed by the teacher and the student in the process of distance learning, and a program that shows the order in which distance learning tools are used to perform these actions. This is similar to the curriculum in classical education. The difference is that in the teaching scenario, it is also considered how to use educational tools and software. .

The following is a teaching scenario that can be offered when using the Moodle educational information system, taking into account its capabilities:

1. The user fills out a questionnaire requesting permission to use the Moodle educational information system.
2. The survey will be reviewed by the OTM information technology center, and the user will be granted the right to use the platform according to the username and password specified in the survey, provided that the requirements for using the system (platform) are met. If the user is a teacher, he is given the right to add a lecture; if a student, this right only allows access to the platform and use of educational materials on it.
3. A student who has access to the platform will be able to enter the platform, familiarize himself with the subjects posted on the platform, become a member of them and study those subjects.
4. To become a member of a science, first select the science you want to become a member of. There will be indicated the name of the subject and the next meeting group and the end date of membership in this group and

the start date of the lesson. Based on this information, the student sends a questionnaire to the teacher. The teacher gives the permission to join the subject, provided that the student fulfills the conditions for membership of the subject.

In the curriculum, the time allocated by the teacher for each lecture, the period for questions to be asked to the teacher about the lecture, the test period for the lecture and the deadline for its completion will be specified.

List of references used:

1. Quvvatov, B. (2024). SQL DATABASES AND BIG DATA ANALYTICS: NAVIGATING THE DATA MANAGEMENT LANDSCAPE. В DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 117–124).
2. Quvvatov, B. (2024). CONSTRUCTION OF SPECIAL MODELS THROUGH DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS AND PRACTICAL SOLUTIONS. В SOLUTION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN MANAGEMENT AND ECONOMY (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 108–115).
3. Quvvatov, B. (2024). FINDING SOLUTIONS OF SPECIAL MODELS BY INTEGRATING INTEGRAL EQUATIONS AND MODELS. В CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 122–130).
4. Quvvatov, B. (2024). GLOBAL IN VIRTUAL LEARNING MOBILE APP CREATION INFORMATION SYSTEMS AND TECHNOLOGIES. В SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 95–104).
5. Quvvatov, B. (2024). WEB FRONT-END AND BACK-END TECHNOLOGIES IN PROGRAMMING. В THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 208–215).
6. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. li.(2023). Mobil ilovalar yaratish va ularni bajarish jarayoni. International journal of scientific researchers, 2(2).
7. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. (2023). USE OF ARTIFICIAL NERVOUS SYSTEMS IN MODELING. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 269-273.
8. Karimov, F. (2022). ANIQ INTEGRALNI TAQRIBIY HISOBLASH. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz), 14(14).
9. Quvvatov, B. (2024). GLOBAL IN VIRTUAL LEARNING MOBILE APP CREATION INFORMATION SYSTEMS AND TECHNOLOGIES. Science and innovation in the education system, 3(1), 95-104.
10. Quvvatov, B. (2024). SQL DATABASES AND BIG DATA ANALYTICS: NAVIGATING THE DATA MANAGEMENT LANDSCAPE. Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 3(1), 117-124.

11. Quvvatov, B. (2024). CONSTRUCTION OF SPECIAL MODELS THROUGH DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS AND PRACTICAL SOLUTIONS. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 3(1), 108-115.
12. Quvvatov, B. (2024). FINDING SOLUTIONS OF SPECIAL MODELS BY INTEGRATING INTEGRAL EQUATIONS AND MODELS. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(1), 122-130.
13. Quvvatov, B. (2024). WEB FRONT-END AND BACK-END TECHNOLOGIES IN PROGRAMMING. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 3(1), 208-215.
14. Behruz Ulugbek og, Q. (2023). TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE: A DYNAMIC PARTNERSHIP. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(11).
15. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED SYSTEM FOR CONTROLLING TEMPERATURE AND HUMIDITY IN PRODUCTION ROOMS. В DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATIONS IN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 84–93).
16. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED PARAMETER CONTROL SYSTEM ROOMS AND WORKSHOPS BASED ON CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES. В ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 2, сс. 16–27).
17. Muradov, O. (2024). BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. В MODELS AND METHODS IN MODERN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 84–93).
18. Muradov, O. (2024). APPLIED TO THE CURRENT TRAINING PROCESS REQUIREMENTS. В INNOVATIVE RESEARCH IN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 54–63).
19. Muradov, O. (2024). APPLICATION OF BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES TO EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES. В МЕЖДУРОДНАЯ КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ АКАДЕМИЧЕСКИХ НАУК (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 46–55).
20. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). DATA BY COMBINING MAIL THROUGH TO SEND METHODS. В THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 198–207).
21. Akhmedova, Z., & Rahmatova, N. (2024). LMS (LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM) LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM FEATURES. В SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 85–94).
22. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). IPHONE OPERATIONAL IN THE SYSTEM MOBILE APPLICATIONS TO CREATE INTENDED PROGRAMMING ENVIRONMENTS. В

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 111–121).

23. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). STRUCTURES OF SMALL DATABASE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS. В SOLUTION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN MANAGEMENT AND ECONOMY (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 97–107).

24. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). CREATION OF A DATABASE FOR THE SYSTEM PLATFORM OF NON-GOVERNMENT EDUCATIONAL CENTERS. В DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 106–116).

25. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). SQL SPECIFICATIONS FOR DATA ANALYSIS. Science and innovation in the education system, 2(13), 113-120.

26. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). DISADVANTAGES OF ELECTRONIC LEARNING. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 2(12), 99-109.

27. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED PARAMETER CONTROL SYSTEM ROOMS AND WORKSHOPS BASED ON CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(2), 16-27.

28. INNOVATIVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND NEW METHODS AND TOOLS FOR THEIR APPLICATION IN TODAY'S EDUCATION

29. OT MURODOV - International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & ..., 2023

30. Jurakulov, S. (2023). PHYSICAL-MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF NA-KMS AND CARBAPOLL BASED GELS. Development and innovations in science, 2(12), 65-70.

31. Jurakulov, S. (2023, December). RESEARCH THEORIES OF PHYSICS COURSES IN JAPAN. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 2, No. 12, pp. 43-48).16:08

